

[Supplementary material]

**Isotopic evidence of an environmental shift at the fall of the Kushite kingdom of Meroë,
Sudan**

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Table S1. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ca}}$ values measured in 64 human and 15 animal samples. The samples were analysed at the Stable Isotope Laboratory, Centre for Arctic Gas Hydrate, Environment and Climate (CAGE), the Arctic University of Norway, Tromsø. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ca}}$ values reported relative to the VPDB standard were re-referenced to the VSMOW standard following Sharp (2007) for comparison with the published data: $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ca, VSMOW}} = (1.03092 \times \delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ca, VPDB}}) + 30.92\text{‰}$.

Human Samples								
Site	Tomb/ID No.	Cultural Period	Sex	Age	Tooth	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ‰ VPDB	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ca}}$ ‰ VPDB	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ca}}$ ‰ VSMOW
El-Kurru	MFA Inv 4608	Meroitic	?	?	M3	-13.55087688	-2.44799121	28.3963169
El-Kurru	MFA Inv 4607	Meroitic	?	?	M2	-13.82596877	-2.736331625	28.099061
Mansourkotti (DDASP DS2)	T.25	Late Meroitic*	M	20–25	M3	-4.147934034	2.279364173	33.26984211
Mansourkotti (DDASP DS2)	T.31	Late Meroitic	M	40–50	M3	-4.388609923	-3.513195949	27.29817603
Mansourkotti (DDASP DS2)	T.31	Late Meroitic	M	40–50	C	-6.126739051	-2.629120255	28.20958735
Mansourkotti (DDASP DS2)	T.78	Late Meroitic	F	40–50	M3	-1.814653514	1.974271012	32.95531547
Korti (DDASP DS128)	T.14	Late Meroitic*	M	35–45	M3	-5.764026088	-0.887886908	30.00465963
Korti (DDASP DS128)	T.16A	Late Meroitic	M	25–30	M3	-5.628053788	1.539660387	32.50726669
Korti (DDASP DS128)	T.16B	Late Meroitic	M	35–45	M2	-6.697542121	-0.033504501	30.88545954
Korti (DDASP DS128)	T.22	Late Meroitic	F	25–30	M3	-2.804789987	-0.988605034	29.9008273
Korti (DDASP DS128)	T.23	Late Meroitic	M	25–30	M3	-3.275288273	2.563132333	33.56238439
Korti (DDASP DS128)	T.26	Late Meroitic	F	16–18	M3	-5.807122741	-3.004891111	27.82219766
Ousli (DDASP DS231)	T.6	Late Meroitic*	F	20–25	M3	-3.646406505	1.63453073	32.60507042
Ousli (DDASP DS231)	T.42	Late Meroitic*	F	25–35	C	-3.890334478	2.440649118	33.43611399
Ousli	T.42	Late Meroitic*	F	25–35	M3	-4.594351641	2.801887332	33.80852169

(DDASP DS231)								
Tabo	T.184	Meroitic (Early)	F	35+	P2	-6.208735685	-4.127716966	26.66465403
Tabo	T.434	Meroitic (Early)	F	35-45	C	-2.9228438	5.078703984	36.15573751
Tabo	T.255	Meroitic (Early)	F	20-30	M3	-4.173732983	1.588533716	32.55765118
Tabo	T.276	Meroitic (Early)	M	35-50	M2	-7.075496925	0.555064369	31.49222696
Tabo	T.295	Meroitic (Early)	F	45+	M3	-6.351706957	1.827330582	32.80383164
Tabo	T.556	Meroitic (Early)	M	25-35	M3	-8.29963305	-0.075002086	30.84267885
Tabo	T.598	Meroitic (Early)	?	33-45	M3	-8.139633643	-0.866493006	30.02671503
Tabo	T.600	Meroitic (Early)	?	20-30	M3	-7.39527687	-0.868735843	30.02440284
Tabo	T.603	Meroitic (Early)*	?	20-30	M3	-9.97270186	-0.010022588	30.90966751
Tabo	T.604	Meroitic (Early)	F	35+	M3	-7.510251056	-1.826531471	29.03699218
Tabo	T.608	Meroitic (Early)	?	35+	M3	-8.127978817	-1.059329997	29.82791552
Tanqasi	T.16	Post-Meroitic	F	30-35	M3	-3.092395267	-4.205224682	26.58474977
Tanqasi	T.23	Late Meroitic*	M	25-35	C	-2.924099226	1.046296135	31.99864761
Tanqasi	T.179	Post-Meroitic	F	45-55	M3	-4.866901458	0.421091502	31.35411165
El-Zuma	T.9	Post-Meroitic**	M	25-30	C	-8.145873778	-1.09443236	29.79172779
El-Zuma	T.9	Post-Meroitic**	M	25-30	M3	-6.305568229	1.890061009	32.8685017
El-Zuma	T.11	Post-Meroitic	?	16-18	M2	-3.409311584	1.703162529	32.67582431
El-Zuma	T.14	Post-Meroitic	F	20-30	M3	-5.106242211	1.455836456	32.42085092
El-Zuma	T.15	Post-Meroitic	F	20-25	C	-4.234730634	-2.982421865	27.84536165
El-Zuma	T.15	Post-Meroitic	F	20-25	M3	-2.960522253	1.017874875	31.96934757
El-Zuma	T.16	Post-Meroitic	M	16-24	C	-6.440108508	-0.703127806	30.19513148
El-Zuma	T.16	Post-Meroitic	M	16-24	M3	-6.85247544	1.287270359	32.24707276
El-Zuma	T.17	Post-Meroitic	M	40-50	C	-4.964531907	2.580995803	33.58080019
El-Zuma	T.17	Post-Meroitic	M	40-50	M2	-2.829572144	2.764021214	33.76948475
El-Zuma	T.20	Post-Meroitic	M	50+	C	-5.478430562	1.916600855	32.89586215
El-Zuma	T.21	Post-Meroitic*	M	35-40	M2	-3.051746433	1.832970396	32.80964584
El-Zuma	T.22	Post-Meroitic	M	35-45	M2	-5.711400002	2.498043034	33.49528252
El-Zuma	T.25	Post-Meroitic	F	25-35	M3	-3.427641779	1.612440649	32.58229731
El-Zuma	T.27	Post-Meroitic**	M	35-45	C	-6.675012337	3.789449649	34.82661943
El-Zuma	T.27	Post-Meroitic**	M	35-45	M3	-7.963630875	2.473320597	33.46979567
El-Detti	T.5	Post-Meroitic	M	40-50	M3	-4.846124214	0.373474783	31.30502262
El-Detti	T.3	Post-Meroitic*	F	30-40	M3	-4.263675087	1.297360129	32.2574745

El-Detti	T.4	Post-Meroitic**	M	45–55	M3	-10.00940573	1.245040606	32.20353726
El-Detti	T.7	Post-Meroitic**	M	40–50	M2	-1.688686212	0.930446936	31.87921636
Hamadab	S 101 #1; HSP 18-04-01	Meroitic	F	20–30	C	-3.929016029	-1.484834666	29.38925425
Hamadab	S 101#1	Meroitic	F	20–30	M3	-1.839243603	0.785121566	31.72939752
Hamadab	S 101#2	Meroitic	M	15–18	M3	-2.374571751	-0.588599163	30.31320135
Hamadab	S 102; HSP 18-05	Meroitic	F	35–45	M2/3	-3.071688433	0.551386018	31.48843487
Hamadab	S 104 #1; HSP 18-06	Meroitic	?	20–45	P	-3.983771914	-2.245853636	28.60470457
Hamadab	S 105 #2; HSP 18-07-0	Meroitic	?	<20	M2/3	-7.33842897	-2.104535068	28.75039271
Hamadab	S 105#1	Meroitic	?	20+	M2	-2.026396519	0.040844782	30.9621077
Hamadab	S 107; HSP 18-09	Meroitic	F	20–30	P	-6.749560961	-0.743142015	30.15388003
Meroe	Grave 1	Post-Meroitic*	M	25–35	M3	-3.92408346	-0.826608797	30.06783246
Toshka	Grave 148/5736	C-Group	?	<19	M3	-9.183782961	1.47413012	32.43971022
Toshka	Grave 108a/T5717a	C-Group	?	<18	M3	-10.4260653	0.886304415	31.83370895
Jebel Moya	3	C-Group Contemporary	F	24–28	M3	-5.036876207	1.305272313	32.26563133
Er-Roseire	T.15	Medieval/Christian*	?	?	P1	-7.086707316	-3.753775177	27.05015809
Hamadab	FN 08 BB 04	Islamic*	?	~6.5	M2	-3.242958575	-0.610763628	30.29035156
Hamadab	HW67DPL1	Islamic*	M	20–25	M3	-4.357229182	-2.99006997	27.83747707
Animal Samples								
Site	Tomb/ID No.	Cultural Period	Species	Sample		$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ‰ VPDB	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ca}}$ ‰ VPDB	$\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{ca}}$ ‰ VSMOW
El-Zuma	T.1	Post-Meroitic	<i>Bos taurus</i> (cattle)	bone		-3.270521084	2.401084976	33.39532652
El-Zuma	T.3: ZS-1	Post-Meroitic	<i>Bos taurus</i> (cattle)	bone		-2.887177216	4.526840898	35.58681082

El-Zuma	T.4: Z4/203	Post-Meroitic	<i>Ovis</i> (sheep)	bone		-6.197506276	2.679446731	33.68229522
El-Zuma	T.4: Z4/193	Post-Meroitic	<i>Bos taurus</i> (cattle)	tooth (M3)		1.543365775	6.351915467	37.46831669
El-Zuma	T.8: ZS-6	Post-Meroitic	<i>Bos taurus</i> (cattle)	bone		-0.340201001	7.4016548	38.55051397
El-Zuma	T.11: ZS-28	Post-Meroitic	<i>Bos taurus</i> (cattle)	bone		-0.273109723	7.702974473	38.86115044
El-Zuma	T.14: Z14/7	Post-Meroitic	<i>Capra/Ovis</i> (goat/sheep)	bone		-4.810494775	5.397534681	36.48442645
El-Zuma	T.20	Post-Meroitic	<i>Ovis</i> (sheep)	bone		-7.565701612	-3.233292531	27.58673406
El-Zuma	T.20	Post-Meroitic	<i>Ovis</i> (sheep)	bone		-3.452341883	2.114861872	33.1002534
El-Zuma	T.24: Z/B/24/6	Post-Meroitic	<i>Ovis</i> (sheep)	bone		-2.271726998	4.353138996	35.40773805
El-Zuma	T.25: ZS-29	Post-Meroitic	<i>Bos taurus</i> (cattle)	bone		-1.37525272	3.140661274	34.15777052
El-Detti	T.1	Post-Meroitic	<i>Ovis</i> (sheep)	bone		-4.854295836	3.716771282	34.75169385
El-Detti	T.2	Post-Meroitic	<i>Canis</i> (dog)	bone		-7.103667153	4.608236631	35.67072331
El-Detti	T.3	Post-Meroitic	<i>Ovis</i> (sheep)	bone		-4.160816455	5.059252285	36.13568437
El-Detti	T.7: DS-4	Post-Meroitic	<i>Bos taurus</i> (cattle)	bone		-4.6129274	4.757064783	35.82415323

*AMS ¹⁴C ages obtained (see Table S2).

** Post-Meroitic $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ outliers.

Table S2. AMS ¹⁴C ages of human remains from the sites of interest. AMS dating was conducted by Poznan Radiocarbon Laboratory and Gliwice Radiocarbon Laboratory (Silesian University of Technology). The radiocarbon ages were modelled in OxCal v.4.2.3 (Poznan) and v.4.3 (Gliwice), using IntCal13 calibration curve (Bronk Ramsey 2009; Reimer *et al.* 2013).

Site and Tomb ID	Material	Lab. No.	Uncalibrated age ¹⁴ C (BP)	Calibrated age (BC/AD) at % probability
El-Detti T.3	bone	Poz-101748	1585±30	AD 406–544 at 95.4%
El-Detti T.5	bone	Poz-101883	1680±30	AD 339–401 at 68.2%
El-Zuma T.21	bone	Poz-101746	1615±30	AD 387–538 at 95.4%
Er-Roseires 18 T.15	bone	Poz-101743	1135±30	AD 885–969 at 68.2%
Hamadab FN 08 BB 004	bone	Poz-107118	170±30	AD 1659–1916 at 95.4%
Hamadab HW67 PL1 HSP 18-11	bone	Poz-100851	140±30	AD 1669–1945 at 95.4%
Jebel Moya SK3	tooth	GdA-5760	3880±40	2470–2210 BC at 95.4%
Korti T.14	bone	Poz-101747	1855±30	AD 82–234 at 95.4%
Korti T.23	bone	Poz-101751	1890±30	AD 56–217 at 95.4%
Mansourkotti T.25	bone	Poz-101749	1935±30	AD 1–130 at 95.4%
Mansourkotti T.35	bone	Poz-101744	1835±30	AD 86–246 at 95.4%
Meroe Grave 1	tooth	GdA-5763	1520±45	AD 424–624 at 95.4%
Ousli T.6	tooth	GdA-5762	1720±40	AD 235–406 at 95.4%
Ousli T.42	bone	GdA-5758	1740±30	AD 236–386 at 95.4%
Tabo T.603	bone	Poz-101742	2120±30	196–106 BC at 68.2%
Tanqasi T.23	bone	GdA-5756	1730±35	AD 235–395 at 95.4 %

References

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